

ORIGINAL CONTRIBUTION

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Anti-dermatophyte activity of *Pelargonium graveolens* essential oils against dermatophytes

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Abstract

Background: *Pelargonium graveolens* as valuable aromatic plant is used for extracting the essential oil, which their biological effects such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and wound healing effects have been confirmed.

Methods: In this study, the anti-dermatophyte effects of nine *P. graveolens* essential oils were confirmed against *Microsporum canis*, *M. gypseum*, *Trichophyton rubrum*, *T. mentagrophytes*, and *T. schoenleinii* by mycelium growth inhibition percent and micro-broth dilution assays. The chemical composition of essential oils was determined by GC and GC-MS.

Results: The main components of *P. graveolens* essential oils and their percentages changed from one sample to others. The highest growth inhibition percent and the lowest MIC values of *P. graveolens* essential oils for dermatophytes were for E₂₀ with 95% geraniol content, followed by E₄ and E₁₄ with highest amounts of geraniol (21%) and citronellol (30–35%) contents.

Conclusion: Therefore, the use of *P. graveolens* essential oils with high geraniol and citronellol is recommended for dermatophytes. Animal models studies of dermatophytes are required to confirm the efficacy and application of *P. graveolens* essential oils in human studies.

Keywords: *P. graveolens*, Essential oil, Geraniol, Citronellol, Dermatophytes

Introduction

Pelargonium genus as perennial small shrubs comprises more than 250 species [1], *P. graveolens* (*Pelargonium roseum*) is highly valued by industries for producing geranium essential oil [2]. According to BS ISO 4371-2012, *P. graveolens* essential oil from different geographical origins should have geraniol (5–20%), citronellol (18–43%), citronellyl formate (4–12%), geranyl formate (1–8%), and linalool (2–11%) as the main components [3]. The chemical profile of *P. graveolens* essential oil is affected from its geographical origin. The pharmacological effects of *P. graveolens* essential oil such as antioxidant [4, 5], antimicrobial [6–9], anti-inflammatory [10, 11] and wound healings [12] activities

is well documented. Furthermore, evaluation the anti-fungal activities of *P. graveolens* essential oil have been the subject of different experimental studies [13–16]. The antifungal activities of *P. graveolens* essential oil were confirmed against *Trichophyton* spp. [15], and *Candida albicans* [13, 14, 16]. Although, there are one report on anti-dermatophyte effects of *P. graveolens* essential oil against *Trichophyton* spp. [15], but there is no investigation to compare the anti-dermatophyte effects of *P. graveolens* essential oils against different kinds of dermatophytes (*Microsporum canis*, *M. gypseum*, *Trichophyton rubrum*, *T. mentagrophytes*, and *T. schoenleinii*).

Dermatophytes (*Trichophyton*, *Microsporum*, *Epidermophyton*) are one of major cause of superficial fungal infections with an estimate lifetime risk of 20–25% [17]. The use of topical and systemic drugs (Azoles/allylamines, terbinafine) is used for treatment of dermatophytes that are associated with adverse effects and

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appearance of resistant microbial strains [18]. Different kinds of essential oils have been evaluated against dermatophytes. *Prunus armeniaca*, *Prunus dulcis var. amara*, *Olea europaea*, *Mentha piperita* [19], *Artemisia sieberi* [20], *Juniperus communis ssp. alpina*, *J. oxycedrus ssp. oxycedrus* and *J. turbinata* [21] were effective against dermatophytes.

Therefore, the subject of this study was to evaluate the anti-dermatophyte effects of nine different *P. graveolens* essential oils from Iran, Germany and India against dermatophytes.

Materials and methods

P. graveolens essential oils

Nine different *P. graveolens* essential oils with identified chemical profiles as Table 1 were used in this study. Essential oils were prepared by Barijessence Pharmaceutical Company (Kashan, Iran). The chemical compositions of essential oil were determined by Quality Control of BarijEssence Pharmaceutical Company, Kashan, Iran.

Dermatophytes strains

Microsporium canis PTCC (Persian Type Culture Collection) 5069, *Microsporium gypseum* PTCC 5070, *Trichophyton rubrum* PTCC 5143, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* PTCC 5054, and *Trichophyton schoenleinii* PTCC 5221 were used in this study. For preparing the dermatophytes, they were cultured on Sabauraud dextrose agar and the cultures were incubated at 22.5 ± 2.5 °C for 14 days. After growth of dermatophytes, suspensions of dermatophytes were prepared in normal saline with 0.05% polysorbate-80. This suspension was used for further antifungal evaluations.

Anti-dermatophyte activity of *P. graveolens* essential oils by mycelium growth inhibition method

P. graveolens essential oils (200 ppm) were incorporated into Sabauraud dextrose agar. Sabauraud dextrose agar without essential oils was used as controls. Then, the fungal patches were prepared by spreading the dermatophyte suspensions on the surface of Sabauraud dextrose agar and were incubated for 7 days at 25 °C in aerobic condition. The surface of cultured media (6 mm) were punched and put on the surface of Sabauraud dextrose agar with or without *P. graveolens* essential oils. The plates were incubated at the same conditions for 7 days. The mycelium growth inhibitions were measured for each plate and the growth inhibition percent were calculated from comparison between the growth in Sabauraud dextrose agar with or without essential oils. The experiment were replicated five times and the means of replicates were used in calculations [22].

Anti-dermatophytes evaluations by micro-broth dilution assay

For determining the Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimal fungicidal concentration (MFC) of *P. graveolens* essential oils, each essential oil were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and serially diluted in RPMI broth media (8–0.015 µl/ml) in 96 micro-titer plates. Then, the adjusted dermatophyte suspensions (10^3 – 10^4 CFU/ml) in RPMI by spectrophotometric method was added to the wells of plates containing essential oil's serial dilutions, and was incubated at 22.5 ± 2.5 °C for 5 days. The lowest concentration of essential oil with visible fungal growth inhibition was defined as Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and the first dilution with

Table 1 The chemical composition of *P. graveolens* essential oils

<i>P. graveolens</i> Essential oil	Main components	Source
E3	Citronellol (29.5%), linalool (13.4%), geraniol (10.6%), citronellyl formate (7.9%), geranyl formate (10.8%), geranyl acetate (7.2%), limonene (5%)	Germany
E4	Citronellol (30.2%), Geraniol (21.9%), linalool (11.04%), citronellyl formate (5%), geranyl formate (3.4%)	India
E20	Geraniol (95.6%), Trans-caryophyllene (3.5%), geranyl formate (1.6%), linalool (0.7%), citronellyl formate (0.3%), citronellol (0.2%)	India
E6	Citronellol (41%), citronellyl formate (12.7%), geraniol (8%), geranyl formate (2.1%), linalool (1%)	Zanjan, Iran
E9	Citronellol (48%), citronellyl formate (16.2%), geraniol (5.1%), geranyl formate (3%), linalool (1.1%)	Delijan, Markazi Province, Iran
E11	Citronellol (45.6%), citronellyl formate (14.1%), geraniol (3.4%), geranyl formate (1.6%), linalool (0.8%)	Shahrood, Iran
E14	Citronellol (34.7%), geraniol (21.3%), citronellyl formate (7.4%), linalool (6.3%), geranyl formate (4.4%), geranyl acetate (1.5%)	Mashhad-E-Ardehal, Isfahan Province, Iran
E21	Citronellol (48.3%), citronellyl formate (10.9%), geraniol (8.4%), linalool (2.2%), geranyl formate (1.7%)	Noorabad, Fars Province, Iran
E22	Citronellol (39.9%), citronellyl formate (13.4%), geraniol (4.2%), geranyl formate (2.8%), linalool (1.3%)	Dezfool, Iran

no growth after culturing on Sabouraud dextrose Agar was Minimal Fungicidal Concentration (MFC). The experiments were replicated three times [22].

Results and discussion

Essential oils are favorable natural compounds that can be used as natural alternative treatment for management of dermatophytosis. Citronellol (0.2–48.3%), geraniol (3.4–95.6%), citronellyl formate (0.3–16.2%), geranyl formate (1.6–10.8%), and linalool (0.7–13.4%) were the main components of 9 samples of *P. graveolens* essential oils (Table 1). The highest and lowest amounts of geraniol (95.6%) and citronellol (0.2%) were found in *P. graveolens* essential oil E₂₀ from India. Trans-caryophyllene was the second main component of this essential oil (3.5%), followed by geranyl formate (1.6%), and linalool (0.7%). The highest amounts of citronellol were in *P. graveolens* essential oil E₂₁ (48.3%), E₉ (48.0%), E₁₁ (45.6%), and E₆ (41%).

Citronellol was the first main component of 8 samples of *P. graveolens* essential oils, while geraniol was the second main component of 2 samples of *P. graveolens* essential oils (E₄ and E₁₄). Linalool was the second main component of one sample *P. graveolens* essential oil. Citronellyl formate was found in 5 samples of *P. graveolens* essential oil as the second main component.

The chemical profiles and main components of *P. graveolens* essential oil were changed from one sample to others. The chemical profile of *P. graveolens* essential oils were not according to standard *P. graveolens* essential oil (BS ISO 4371-2012) [3].

The anti-dermatophyte effects of *P. graveolens* essential oils against dermatophytes by mycelium growth inhibition test exhibited that *P. graveolens* essential oil E₂₀ had the highest mycelium growth inhibition percent against dermatophytes (30.9–53.3%), followed by E₄ (17.8–43.6%) and E₁₄ (19.9–43.6%), respectively. *T. rubrum* had the higher mycelium inhibition percent (22.5–53.3%) by *P. graveolens* essential oils, followed by *M. gypseum* (17–45.4%), and *T. mentagrophytes* (16.5–

43.6%). *M. canis* and *T. schoenleinii* had the less mycelium inhibition percent by *P. graveolens* essential oils (Table 2).

In micro-broth dilution assay, the MIC and MFC values for E₂₀ were in the ranges of 0.03–0.125 and 0.06–0.25 µl/ml, respectively. E₁₄ (MIC, MFC values of 0.06–0.125, 0.125–0.25 µl/ml), E₄ and E₂₁ (MIC, MFC values of 0.06–0.25, 0.125–0.5 µl/ml) showed anti-dermatophyte activity, followed by E₁₁, E₉ (MIC, MFC values of 0.125–0.25, 0.125–0.5 µl/ml), E₃ (MIC, MFC values of 0.125–0.25, 0.25–0.5) µl/ml), E₆ (MIC, MFC values of 0.125–0.5, 0.25–0.5 µl/ml). E₂₂ (MIC, MFC values of 0.125–0.5, 0.25–1 µl/ml) had the higher MIC and MFC values against dermatophytes than the others (Table 3).

As the results of anti-dermatophyte screening exhibited that E₂₀ with high amount of geraniol had the highest activity against dermatophytes, followed by E₄, E₁₄. Indeed the *P. graveolens* essential oils with high amount of citronellol and geraniol as the first and second main components had the higher anti-dermatophyte effects. The essential oil with high amounts of citronellol or citronellyl formate showed anti-dermatophytes effects lower than the essential oils with citronellol and geraniol as the main components.

The results of anti-dermatophyte effects of *P. graveolens* essential oils have not been in according to their anti-candidal effects. There was no significant difference in anti-candidal activities of six samples of *P. graveolens* essential oils with citronellol (7.7–43.7%) and geraniol (19.3–48.5%) against clinical isolates of *C. albicans* in regard to inhibition zone diameters and the MIC and MFC values [23].

The results of this study confirmed that corresponding components responsible for anti-dermatophyte activity of *P. graveolens* essential oils were geraniol and citronellol. The mechanism of action for geraniol and citronellol is interfering with cell membrane of dermatophytes and decreasing the ergosterol content of cell by inhibition of ergosterol biosynthesis [24, 25], while the anti-candidal

Table 2 Mycelium growth inhibition of dermatophytes by 200 ppm *P. graveolens* essential oils

<i>P. graveolens</i> Essential oil	<i>T. schoenleinii</i>	<i>M. gypseum</i>	<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>	<i>T. rubrum</i>	<i>M. canis</i>
E21	15.9	17.0	16.5	22.5	17.2
E6	14.5	23.1	20.4	31.8	13.9
E22	9.8	18.7	22.6	28.5	10.3
E14	19.9	25	22.8	35.0	16.0
E20	30.9	45.4	36.3	53.3	41.4
E3	14.0	20.7	15.8	28.5	11.3
E11	20.5	20.0	19.5	28.8	8.8
E4	17.8	23.3	43.6	26.8	16.1
E9	14.9	18.0	31.0	27.6	17.2

Table 3 The antifungal activity of *P. graveolens* essential oils against dermatophytes

<i>P. graveolens</i> essential oil	<i>T. schoenleinii</i>		<i>M. canis</i>		<i>M. gypseum</i>		<i>T. mentagrophytes</i>		<i>T. rubrum</i>	
	MIC	MFC	MIC	MFC	MIC	MFC	MIC	MFC	MIC	MFC
E3	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.5	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.5
E4	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.06	0.125	0.25	0.5
E6	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.5
E9	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.5
E11	0.125	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.25	0.25	0.5
E14	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.25	0.06	0.125	0.125	0.25	0.125	0.25
E20	0.06	0.125	0.125	0.25	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.125	0.125	0.25
E21	0.125	0.125	0.125	0.5	0.125	0.25	0.06	0.125	0.25	0.25
E22	0.125	0.125	0.25	0.5	0.25	0.5	0.25	0.5	0.5	0.5
Amphotericin	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.5	1	0.5	0.5

MIC Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (µl/ml), MFC Minimal Fungicidal Concentration (µl/ml)

activity against *C. albicans* is not mediated by ergosterol biosynthesis [26].

Conclusions

Therefore, for preparing anti-dermatophyte products containing *P. graveolens* essential oils, the use of essential oil with main components of geraniol (30–35%) and citronellol (21%) are recommended. The third main component of essential oil should be linalool or citronellyl formate in higher percentage of 5%. More studies are required for comparing the efficacy of *P. graveolens* essential oils in animal studies.

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Authors' contributions

Mehdi Valian prepared and analyzed the essential oils; Mohaddese Mahboubi supervised the study and wrote the manuscript.

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Not applicable.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

The authors declare their consent for publication.

Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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References

- Watt JM, Breyer-Brandwijk MG. In: the University of Michigan: Livingstone, editor. The medicinal and poisonous plants of southern and eastern Africa being an account of their medicinal and other uses, chemical composition, pharmacological effects and toxicology in man and animal; 1962.
- Lis-Balchin M. Geranium and *Pelargonium*: the genera Geranium and *Pelargonium*: Taylor & Francis; 2002.
- BS-ISO-4731. Essential oil of geranium (*Pelargonium* × ssp.). 2012.
- Cavar S, Maksimović M. Antioxidant activity of essential oil and aqueous extract of *Pelargonium graveolens* L'Her. Food Control. 2012;23(1):263–7.
- Ben Slima A, Ali MB, Barkallah M, Traore AI, Boudawara T, Allouche N, et al. Antioxidant properties of *Pelargonium graveolens* L'Her essential oil on the reproductive damage induced by deltamethrin in mice as compared to alpha-tocopherol. Lipids Health Dis. 2013;12:30.
- Carmen G, Hancu G. Antimicrobial and antifungal activity of *Pelargonium roseum* essential oils. Advanced pharmaceutical bulletin. 2014;4(Suppl 2): 511–4.
- Lis-Balchin M, Buchbauer G, Hirtenlehner T, Resch M. Antimicrobial activity of *Pelargonium* essential oils added to a quiche filling as a model food system. Lett Appl Microbiol. 1998;27(4):207–10.
- Andrade MA, Cardoso MG, Batista LR, Freire JM, Nelson DL. Antimicrobial activity and chemical composition of essential oil of *Pelargonium odoratissimum*. Rev Bras. 2011;21:47–52.
- Mahboubi M, Kazempour N, Farzin N. Antimicrobial activity of *Pelargonium graveolens* and *Oliveria decumbens* extracts against clinical isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus*. Journal of Biologically Active Products from Nature. 2011;1(2):105–11.
- Katiyar SK, Mukhtar H. Green tea polyphenol (–)-epigallocatechin-3-gallate treatment to mouse skin prevents UVB-induced infiltration of leukocytes, depletion of antigen-presenting cells, and oxidative stress J Leukoc Biol. 2001;69(5):719–26.
- Boukhatem MN, Kameli A, Ferhat MA, Saidi F, Mekarnia M. *Rose geranium* essential oil as a source of new and safe anti-inflammatory drugs. The Libyan journal of medicine. 2013;8:22520.
- Mahboubi M, Feizabadi MM, Khamechian T, Kazempour N, Razavi Zadeh M, Sasani F, et al. The effect of *Oliveria decumbens* and *Pelargonium graveolens* on healing of infected skin wounds in mice. World journal of plastic surgery. 2016;5(3):259–64.
- Rosato A, Vitali C, Piarulli M, Mazzotta M, Argentieri MP, Mallamaci R. In vitro synergic efficacy of the combination of nystatin with the essential oils of *Origanum vulgare* and *Pelargonium graveolens* against some *Candida* species. Phytomedicine : international journal of phytotherapy and phytopharmacology. 2009;16(10):972–5.
- Rosato A, Vitali C, Gallo D, Balenzano L, Mallamaci R. The inhibition of *Candida* species by selected essential oils and their synergism with

- amphotericin B. *Phytomedicine : international journal of phytotherapy and phytopharmacology*. 2008;15(8):635–8.
15. Shin S, Lim S. Antifungal effects of herbal essential oils alone and in combination with ketoconazole against *Trichophyton* spp. *J Appl Microbiol*. 2004;97(6):1289–96.
 16. Mahboubi M, Feizabadi M, Safara M. Antifungal activity of essential oils from *Zataria multiflora*, *Rosmarinus officinalis*, *Lavandula stoechas*, *Artemisia sieberi* Besser and *Pelargonium graveolens* against clinical isolates of *Candida albicans*. *Pharmacogn Mag*. 2008;4(15):15–8.
 17. Oke OO, Onayemi O, Olasode OA, Omisore AG, Oninla OA. The prevalence and pattern of superficial fungal infections among school children in Ile-Ife, South-Western Nigeria %J. *Dermatology Research and Practice*. 2014;2014:7.
 18. Kaul S, Yadav S, Dogra S. Treatment of Dermatophytosis in elderly, children, and pregnant women. *Indian Dermatol Online J*. 2017;8(5):310–8.
 19. Ibrahim SY, Abd El-Salam MM. Anti-dermatophyte efficacy and environmental safety of some essential oils commercial and in vitro extracted pure and combined against four keratinophilic pathogenic fungi. *Environ Health Prev Med*. 2015;20(4):279–86.
 20. Mahboubi M. *Artemisia sieberi* Besser essential oil and treatment of fungal infections. *Biomedicine & pharmacotherapy = Biomedecine & pharmacotherapie*. 2017;89:1422–30.
 21. Cavaleiro C, Pinto E, Gonçalves MJ, Salgueiro L. Antifungal activity of Juniperus essential oils against dermatophyte, *Aspergillus* and *Candida* strains. *J Appl Microbiol*. 2006;100(6):1333–8.
 22. Mahboubi M, HeidaryTabar R, Mahdizadeh E. The anti-dermatophyte activity of *Zataria multiflora* essential oils. *J Med Mycol*. 2017;27(2):232–7.
 23. Mahboubi M, Mahdizadeh E, HeidaryTabar R. The anti-candidal activity of *Pelargonium graveolens* essential oils against clinical isolates of *Candida albicans*. *Infectio*. 2018;22:1.
 24. Pereira Fde O, Mendes JM, Lima IO, Mota KS, Oliveira WA, Lima Ede O. Antifungal activity of geraniol and citronellol, two monoterpenes alcohols, against *Trichophyton rubrum* involves inhibition of ergosterol biosynthesis. *Pharm Biol*. 2015;53(2):228–34.
 25. Ismail H. Novel antifungal activity of geraniol and its synergistic effect in combination with fluconazole against resistant *Candida albicans*. Worcester Polytechnic Institute 2012; Bachelor of Science.
 26. Leite MC, de Brito Bezerra AP, de Sousa JP, de Oliveira Lima E. Investigating the antifungal activity and mechanism(s) of geraniol against *Candida albicans* strains. *Med Mycol*. 2015;53(3):275–84.

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